

Desire Kirabo
Ruth Keza

THE GLOBAL IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON THE ACCESS TO SEXUAL AND REPRODUCTIVE HEALTH TOOLS (CONTRACEPTIVES)

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AUTHORS:RUTH KEZA & DESIRE KIRABO

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List of Abbreviations

COVID-19: Corona virus disease 2019

SRH: Sexual and Reproductive Health

CHW: Community Health Workers

WHO: World Health Organization

NCD's: Non- Communicable Diseases

HPV: Human Papillomavirus

LMICs: Low and Middle Income Countries

STIs: Sexually transmitted infections

LARC: Long-acting reversible contraception

PIASCY: Presidential Initiative on AIDS Strategy for Communication to Youth

Executive Summary

As the pandemic made global impact impacted different African regions, many countries faced a sudden 'lockdown'. With populations confined to their own homes, organizations of all types had to change the way they operated or shut down entirely, with little or no time to prepare. This impacted the global economy, which has also resulted in the loss of millions of lives and has disrupted normal day-to-day functioning with the various restrictions like lockdowns, isolation, and confinement that were used as measures to reduce its spread.³ COVID-19 regulations and restrictions limited the movement of and contact between humans which brought on other challenges such as the disruption of access to different essential services like education, food, and health care. The access of sexual reproductive tools became too hard mostly for people living in Africa was so hard mostly to those in rural parts of countries such as Rwanda, Uganda and Kenya.

Some of the sexual reproductive tools that were so inefficient include contraceptives . This lack was mostly due to several reasons including the closure of hospitals and health care centers due to the urge of preventing the spread of COVID-19. Moreso, there was a lag in the supply chain of contraceptives since the transport system was shut down in several African countries. To add on, research shows that there was a shift in the allocation of the already limited resources in Africa. Some of the resources that were supposed to cater for the sexual reproduction sector got transferred to other emergency points of COVID-19. For example, most of the nurses were too busy concentrating on dealing with the COVID-19-emergencies yet they gave little or no attention to the sexual reproductive health aspects.

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This resulted in both positive and negatives effects on the lives of the people although most of the effects were adverse since many people got bogged down in a quagmire of misery. For example, this led to the increase in early pregnancies since most of the youth were out of school and couldn't access contraceptives back in their homes. Moreso, there was an increase in population yet also death rate since many people died through the process of abortions for people who did not want to retain the unborn babies. Other results include high risks of contacting Sexually transmitted infections. However, due to the health hazards related to contraceptives including infertility and several body disorders, it is reported that many females survived this curse as they had no access to contraceptive pills.

Due to this quagmire of paradoxes, several countries and organizations have stood up to mitigate these catastrophes in order to save people. For example, in Uganda trained teachers then mobilized young people within their communities to attend the sexuality education sessions held in various community locations outside schools. Other countries like Rwanda used Community health workers to help with the distribution and guidance of contraceptives in their respective local areas. In North Carolina, USA they used Telehealth to reach people and do consultation on the use of different contraceptives and for different needs relating to Sexual and reproductive health. At the end of this study, after examining different interventions performed, we also recommend that contraceptives can be added to list of basic needs like food that are distributed to people door to door during a health threat. We also recommend Telehealth to give guidance on the use of different contraceptives, to advice people on the nearest place to acquire contraceptives and tell them those that are affordable according to each person's income.

Introduction

Corona Viruses are a diverse group of viruses that can cause illnesses ranging from coughs and colds to more serious diseases.¹ In December 2019, there was a new corona virus that was identified in Wuhan, and because of its rapid global spread, the World Health Organization (WHO) declared it a pandemic on March 11th 2020 and also named it “Corona Virus disease 2019” (COVID-19).² COVID-19 has impacted the global economy, which has also resulted in the loss of millions of lives and has disrupted normal day to day functioning with the various restrictions like lockdowns, isolation and confinement that were used as measures to reduce its spread.³ COVID-19 regulations and restrictions limited the movement of and contact between humans which brought on other challenges such as the disruption of access to different essential services like education, food and health.⁴

Access to healthcare services was impacted during the COVID-19 even in countries with strong health systems capacity for various reasons.⁵ Some healthcare providers had to be cut off, patients faced difficulty reaching the facility due to lockdowns, many resources were relocated to treating and testing COVID-19 and people feared getting into contact with healthcare providers and facilities due to fear of contamination.⁵ Additionally, COVID-19 has disturbed the supply distribution of necessary medicines. Some of the health services that were most affected were access to mental health services, treatment of other noncommunicable diseases (NCDs), and access to family planning services and contraception.⁶ WHO conducted a survey which reported that in 68% of countries, family planning services were disrupted. 32% of the countries surveyed reported a disruption in facility-based birth services.⁷

Limited access to contraceptives deprives women of child bearing age of their ability to acquire contraceptives if they do not wish to become pregnant and this has various consequences.⁸ For instance, unmet contraceptive needs is the main cause of short inter-pregnancy intervals, which are the periods between the last delivery and the next conception of a child for a woman. This can also lead to early childbearing, physical abuse, unintended pregnancy, and poor maternal and child health outcomes.⁸ Furthermore, unintended pregnancies can lead to depression of the mother as they would also feel stressed from the thought of being a parent.⁹

Not only do contraceptives like condoms protect from unintended pregnancies but also from the spread and transmission of sexually transmitted infections (STIs).¹⁰ STIs can be transmitted from mother to child in pregnancy and this can bring on negative outcomes, including still birth, prematurity and congenital defects.¹⁰ STIs like Human papillomavirus (HPV) causes cervical cancer which is a very common cancer among women and it has caused 342,000 deaths in the year of 2020 and majority of these deaths occur in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs).¹¹

Given the role of contraceptives in averting these challenges, and the disruption of health services during COVID-19, this research intends to identify obstacles to accessing sexual and reproductive health (SRH) tools during the Covid-19 pandemic and the consequences of this limited access. With that will come recommendations for the maintenance of SRH service delivery during the next health threat.

Research question

What is the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on access to contraceptives and what can be done to prevent disruption during future health threats?

Objectives of the research

- a. To identify the obstacles to accessing SRH tools during the Covid-19 pandemic.
- b. To evaluate the consequences of limited access to SRH tools
- c. To provide recommendations on the maintenance of SRH service delivery during the next pandemic

Methods

This research paper is a desk review of scientific literature databases including PubMed, PubMed central, Medline and open google searches. The search terms include: “COVID-19”, “Pandemic”, “Global impact”, “Disruption”, “health services”, “contraceptives”, “condoms”, “unintended pregnancy”, “limited access” “Sexual reproductive health”. The articles that will be obtained from those search terms will be summarized to deduce relevant information related to the topic of “Global impact of COVID-19 on access to sexual and reproductive health tools”. The summary of articles about the disruption of health services during the pandemic will be mainly focused on those in relation to the access of contraceptives. In our searches we excluded articles that talked about sexual reproductive health services beyond access to contraceptives such as “postnatal care”, “access to anti-retroviral” and “supply of safe delivery products.” In

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addition, articles relating to recommendations to mitigate the pandemic effects will be also selected to offer solutions in preparation of future health threats. We searched and read articles that were released within these last 6 years because we wanted to understand the issues related to access to contraceptives before the COVID-19 pandemic and whether or not COVID-19 worsened the situation.

Results

Factors that contributed to limited access to SRH tools

Previous public health emergencies have shown that the impact of an epidemic on sexual and reproductive health includes not just the direct, negative impacts on a person's health but also includes the indirect and unintended consequences as well.¹² During the COVID-19 pandemic, these indirect impacts were seen with lockdowns, diversion of sexual health workers to other aspects of health concern, lag in the supply chains of sexual reproductive tools and limited sexual education.¹²

The pandemic led to an economic instability that made people desire less to reproduce as they were already having hardships in affording food and other health services for themselves.¹³ People had difficulties in accessing basic needs which brought in them the need to avoid multiplying the number of people they have to cater for by reproducing, therefore, required contraceptives to avoid pregnancies. However, access to condoms in most countries was limited mainly due to lockdowns and social distancing restrictions which were measures used to reduce the spread.¹³

Performance Monitoring for Action (PMA) conducted a study on the disruption of health services and contraception access during the COVID-19 pandemic and found that there were various reasons why people had limited access to contraception. Those reasons involved; closure of doctor's offices, inability to obtain appointments with doctors, difficulty of getting

transportation to the healthcare services, government restrictions on movement and the fear of being infected.¹⁴ More results of this survey showed that it was difficult to make money during the COVID-19 pandemic, which pushed people to use the little money they earn to buy food instead of condoms.¹⁴ Some of the respondents mentioned that they feared visiting the hospitals because once they were there, before receiving any service, they had to be tested for corona virus and if found with it, they were sent for quarantine ¹⁴

The closure of clinics also hindered the access to contraceptive care services and this was a reported issue in several countries from all continents of the world including the following countries: Zambia, Pakistan, Malaysia, Germany, Sri Lanka, Uganda, Colombia, Zimbabwe, Sudan, Ghana, El Salvador. There were more than 100 clinic closures that were reported in those countries.¹⁵ During the pandemic, equipment and staff involved in provision of sexual and reproductive health services got diverted to fulfill other needs.¹² The global supply and distribution of condoms was not seen as essential during the COVID-19 pandemic, thus limiting its access and use among women and men.¹⁶

The supply chain of sexual and reproductive health tools between manufacturers and developing countries that depend on imports was disrupted during the COVID-19 pandemic. For example, in India the exports of pharmaceutical ingredients were being limited so as to give priority to others and among these drugs that were not prioritized there is the “hormone progesterone” which is essential in the manufacturing of contraceptive pills and Intra Uterine Devices.¹⁵ This resulted in the limited production of these essential pills.

Furthermore, due to limited sexual reproductive tools, some people and organizations started taking an economic advantage of the situation. There was an increment in unwanted contraceptive pathways, unmet need for sexually transmitted infection (STI) testing, and switches from freely provided to commercially sold condoms and contraception.¹⁷ As the economy continued to recess during the COVID-19 pandemic, the people or organizations responsible for supplying sexual reproductive tools freely started to sell them. This is because they thought it could be a big commercial deal for them to survive.¹⁷

Disproportionate impact of COVID-19 on access to SRH tools for different social population groups

The limited access to contraceptives affected people from different populations in different ways. Some people were more vulnerable than others even when they live in the same country and some actually benefitted from the situation. A study carried out by Bolarinwa showed that in South African those in the 3rd wealth quantile were more affected by the hardships to acquire condoms during the COVID-19 pandemic compared to those in the first levels of wealth quantile.¹³ The access to contraceptives also affected gravely the youth in Scotland where some contraceptives were initially being provided for free to the youth but were commercialized during the pandemic.¹⁷ These contraceptives were being commercialized as a way of increasing the money earned by those sellers because COVID-19 had also affected their sales.

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An online survey identified that the access to contraceptives was also made accessible to people who could afford it economically when certain agencies decided to connect pharmacies with people online. This signified that some could put an online pharmacy order for contraceptives and have them delivered to their home without having to go there physically and this was helpful with the limited movements and restrictions put up by the government.¹⁷ And of course such services were only benefitted by those aware of them, those whose have access to internet and those who can afford them.

Consequences of limited access to SRH tools

COVID-19 brought about different changes as mentioned above like movement restrictions, closures of clinics and lockdowns that disrupted supply chains of SRH tools and thus access them and this led to different consequences. With movements restricted due to COVID-19 and reduced visits to health facilities due to various reasons, people who preferred to use long-acting reversible contraception (LARC) methods were deprived of it for some time.¹⁵ LARC methods include intrauterine devices, injections, and birth control implants which are contraceptives for women that can last for several years¹⁸. For one to use LARC methods, they need to visit a doctor who will assist them with the process and since the COVID-19 pandemic limited movements and visits to health facilities the access to these methods was disrupted.¹⁵

Although elements of SRH services were deemed essential to keep running during lockdown, public health messaging to only seek help for essential services and reduce pressure on general practice and pharmacy services appears to have been problematic as young people were unsure

what counted as essential care. This led some to self-censor their need (e.g., for contraceptive care) which resulted in certain consequences including discontinuing contraception, with potential implications for unintended conceptions and abortion.¹⁷

A report of study made on 6 focal countries shows that COVID-19 has disrupted the access to contraceptives in many countries all over the world including Burkina Faso, Syria, Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), Bangladesh, Nigeria, and Columbia.¹⁹ Due to supply chain problems and access issues, contraceptive access and use have also been significantly impacted in Colombia and the DRC. The disruption of global supply and distribution of condoms resulted in unintended pregnancies and increased risks of getting HIV for certain people like Sex workers, and adolescents and pregnant women.^{16,20}

The COVID-19 pandemic is blamed for the early teenage pregnancies that occurred in the past two years.²¹ Due to the fact that most of the schools were locked down during the pandemic, many of the school children returned to their homes. Most of these youth who stayed in rural areas could definitely not access such reproductive health tools which they used to access at their schools.²¹ This is because such tools are normally found in urban centers. Therefore, many girls and boys unintentionally got into sexual intercourses without any birth control protection tools. A teacher in Uganda, has claimed that more than 90,000 girls under 18 got pregnant during the closure of schools during the COVID-19 pandemic.²²

The unmet needs for contraceptives did bring a lot of negative effects, However, to another extent, it is right to observe some of the positive results that a lack of contraceptives might have created.²³ Although most of women got unwanted pregnancies, it can be urged that some of the youth survived engaging in early sexual activities due the fear of early pregnancies by not using protection. This can logically be judged that most of the youth indirectly survived sexual transmitted diseases and kept safe for their future prosperities including their education.²³

Moreso, the shortage of contraceptives saved girls and women from health hazards in a way that contraceptive pills are famously known for their negative implications on human bodies.²⁴ This is more associated with change in the females' hormonal balance that results in severe menstrual bleeding. According to medical news today, this menstrual destruction results in breakthrough bleeding. Here, the blood is usually either light red or dark reddish brown, much like the blood at the beginning or end of a period. Breakthrough bleeding frequently occurs in women who use the contraceptive pills.²⁴

Discussion

Our report examined the changes that occurred during the COVID-19 that affected the way people normally accessed contraceptives globally. The COVID-19 limited the access to contraceptives which caused a lot of consequences including unintended pregnancies, increase early teenage pregnancies, increased spread of STI's and even domestic abuse. All these were

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mainly because there were restrictions put on to reduce the spread of the Corona virus and they made life a bit hard for the population and the economic decline.

The challenges brought on by limited access to contraceptives during the COVID-19 pandemic was also due to not prioritizing sexual and reproductive health services during a health threat and this should be changed.²⁵ This is because the limited access to those services like accessing SRH tools can affect the world in terms of increasing population in an uncontrolled way.²⁶ And also increased health challenges like unsafe abortions which is not good for a population in terms of having a high number of women with health issues or those who die due to that.

To be able to deal with the limited movements during the COVID-19 certain economies like in North Carolina, USA they used Telehealth to offer different health services.²⁷ Those include doctor's appointments for checkups that and guidance in medication taking. This kind of intervention helped a lot people who couldn't access healthcare facilities including those in rural areas to prevent them from travelling long distances. However, it wasn't effective from emergency care and certain treatments like cancer treatments and also people without computers or internet-enabled mobile device couldn't benefit from this.²⁷

Other countries such as Uganda took sex education out of the classroom into villages and communities during the COVID-19 pandemic. Most of the support for such a plan was from the Embassy of the Kingdom of the Netherlands, UNFPA and implementing partner Save the Children International re-purposed.²⁸ This was more of the already existing curriculum, based on

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the Presidential Initiative on AIDS Strategy for Communication to Youth (PIASCY). This was vital in extending sex education sessions to young people both in school and out of school during the COVID-19 pandemic. In eight districts in Northern Uganda and West Nile, 832 teachers from 216 schools were trained to deliver sex education using the PIASCY curriculum.²⁸

The trained teachers then mobilized young people within their communities to attend the sex education sessions held in various community locations. To ensure that the sessions were embraced by the community members, UNFPA and Save the Children oriented the district leadership structures from the Local Councils (LCs) to the district chairpersons and Resident District Commissioners (RDCs) to appraise them of the need to support this intervention. Technical officers from the District Health and Education offices were on ground to monitor the teacher training sessions and the sex education sessions.²⁸

In Rwanda, during the COVID-19 pandemic, community health workers (CHWs) served as front-line workers in the COVID-19 response while maintaining community health services.²⁹ Here the health workers participated in delivering contraceptives that both were supposed to be taken oral and to be injected. Since the women were not able to move from one place to another due to transport restrictions, this was an important role that the village health workers played. They advised the local women on how to take such pills and guided them to make sure they don't miss out on the dose. Most of these health workers were efficiently trained by the Rwandan health system in order to ensure that they deliver efficient sexual health care services to the people.²⁹

As for mitigating these challenges brought on by limited access to contraceptives, we suggest certain interventions. We believe that such an intervention like Telehealth could help access SRH services including SRH tools if applied globally. With Telehealth, people can be guided through what type of contraceptives they can use depending on different preferences and how their body would react to it. This can be achieved by the doctors going through a number of questions with the patients using an internet- enabled mobile device to understand the kind of contraceptive the patient needs which doesn't not involve them to meet in person, examples could be oral pills and condoms. Through Telehealth people can get advice on the nearest places to them to access contraceptives and also the health workers can advise them on which contraceptive to buy according to what they said they can afford.

Another intervention we would suggest is that during a next health threat, distribution of contraceptives should be prioritized like the distribution of food and funds. For instance, different types of contraceptives could be distributed door to door to people as one the basic needs during a pandemic that could similarly also limit movements of people or reduce their income. This type of intervention was made during the COVID-19 in one of the countries in Africa. Rwanda did a door-to-door delivery of free food and other basic needs to its most vulnerable populations so as to protect them from worse vulnerability.³⁰

A similar intervention was performed in Kabul, Afghanistan where the government distributed free bread to its poor population as a way to attend to them.³¹ We believe that a similar

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intervention for contraceptives could be done. For contraceptives like condoms, they could be freely distributed to the homes of people most especially the most vulnerable. And some other types of contraceptives that need prescriptions and administration by a health worker could be offered at the sector's office also for free. And this would also come with allowing minimum movements for those people who need to go to the sector's office for such services. This intervention could not only benefit the most vulnerable but also those who aren't.

Limitations

While we were able to find different articles that helped us write our report, we also faced different difficulties. Those include, articles that were able limited access to contraceptives specifically and not just access to sexual and reproductive health in general. It was also hard to find numerical data about unintended pregnancies, specifically that occurred during the COVID-19 pandemic due to lack of access to contraceptives. And also doing only online research and not having our own field work research made it harder to find reliable resources(articles) to use for all information we wanted to provide.

Conclusion

Access to different health services and tools such as contraceptives was limited during the COVID-19. And this was not only because of viruses' effects on someone's health itself but also because of the changes it brought about in most countries. These changes include governments restrictions to reduce the spread of COVID-19, for example, lockdown, quarantine, limited

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movements with reduced transportation means and a decline in the economy. There were closures of clinics, people feared contacting the virus by visiting healthcare facilities and others to just go out of the house to seek for pharmacy. The access to contraceptives was not prioritized as most health resources were diverted to treating and testing for COVID-19 in most countries and also their supply chains were disrupted. This increased the number of unwanted pregnancies, teenage pregnancies, unsafe abortions, increased HIV spread and change in preferred contraceptives. To be able to cope with such difficulties during a health threat we suggest telehealth for guidance of contraceptives use and free distribution of contraceptives among basic needs that are distributed to people directly to their homes or their sector's office most especially to the more vulnerable.

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